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ASSESSING EXERGY CONSUMPTION IN THE MOBILITY SECTOR: FROM DIRECT FUEL USE TO MATERIAL MANUFACTURING

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1. Abstract

The transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources along with the electrification of transport has increased the demand for materials, particularly metals. This is because modern technologies such as electric batteries and infrastructure for renewable electricity require more metals than previous technological systems. Understanding the exergy costs associated with material production in transportation systems allows us to evaluate how the energy transition impacts the mobility sector, a relatively unexplored area. This study assesses the exergy costs in materials per kilometre travelled and per tonne of load transported in different freight transportation systems, technologies and energy sources. The analyzed cases include road freight transportation, considering diesel and electricity as energy sources. This approach enables a circular thermoeconomic analysis that not only accounts for the direct fuel consumption but also the infrastructure, which plays a critical role in the context of the energy transition. The results provide crucial insights into resource optimization and environmental impact reduction, contributing to the development of strategies that align with global sustainability objectives in the mobility sector. Moreover, the study highlights a shift in material composition between internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEVs) and battery electric vehicles (BEVs), where the latter relies more on strategic metals with higher *Thermodynamic Rarity*. While the electric truck shows higher exergy costs due to valuable metals in its electrical systems, advances in battery technology and energy efficiency could reduce these costs in the future.

Keywords: Circular thermoeconomic analysis, Exergy costs, Material manufacturing, Transportation systems.

2. Introduction

The growing demand for materials, especially critical metals such as lithium, cobalt, nickel, and rare earth elements, has been accelerated by the energy transition and the electrification of the transportation sector [1]. These resources are essential for the development of electric vehicle (EV) batteries and renewable energy infrastructure [2]. According to a report from the International Energy Agency [3], the demand for these metals could increase fivefold by 2040, posing significant challenges regarding resource availability and the environmental impacts arising from their extraction and processing. While these advancements are crucial for mitigating climate change, they also necessitate a deeper evaluation of their implications in terms of sustainability and material efficiency [4]. In addition to the direct impacts of material extraction, the electrification of transportation also affects energy and material consumption throughout the lifecycle of transportation systems.

Recent studies have shown that electric vehicle infrastructure, such as charging stations and the associated power grid, requires substantial amounts of metals like copper and aluminum, which often have a significant environmental footprint due to high CO₂ emissions in their production [5]. Other studies have adopted thermodynamic approaches to assess the exergy costs involved in the production of electric vehicles and their infrastructure. For example, Demirel [6] used exergy analysis to compare the material and energy costs of different transportation technologies, revealing that while electric vehicles exhibit superior energy efficiency during use, the production of batteries and other electronic components demands considerable material investment. This analysis emphasizes the need for a holistic approach that considers not only vehicle usage but also the infrastructure and associated material resources. Regarding emissions reduction, several studies have demonstrated that the electrification of transportation has the potential to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions. According to Hawkins' analysis [7], electric vehicles can cut CO₂ emissions by 50% over their lifecycle compared to internal combustion engine vehicles, particularly when the electricity comes from renewable sources. However, the manufacturing of these vehicles, which depends on materials like lithium and cobalt, could offset these environmental benefits if the impacts associated with the extraction and processing of these resources are not adequately managed [8]. Therefore, the transition to more sustainable transportation requires not only the adoption of cleaner technologies but also the efficient management of critical materials, alongside the development of strategies that minimize environmental impacts throughout the entire lifecycle of transportation systems. In this regard, thermo-economic approaches, which integrate exergy analysis and material lifecycle assessments, are essential for understanding and mitigating the impacts of transportation electrification [9].

Therefore, the objective of this study is to evaluate the material and exergy impacts of transport electrification, focusing particularly on resource efficiency and sustainability throughout the lifecycle of electric vehicles and their infrastructure. The exergy costs in materials per kilometre travelled and per tonne transported are assessed in two freight transport systems, technologies, and energy sources. The analyzed cases include road freight transport, considering diesel and electricity as energy sources.

3. Materials and Methodology

This section describes the materials, data sources, and methodological framework used to assess the exergy costs associated with materials manufacturing in freight transportation systems. The methodology applied in this study consists of a comparison between two automotive technologies: the internal combustion engine and fuel tank of a Volvo FH16 diesel truck (780 HP, 574 kW) and the motor and battery of a Tesla Semi electric truck (1000 HP, 735.5 kW). The aim of this study is to evaluate the exergy cost of the materials that constitute both technologies per kilometre travelled and per tonne of load transported. To achieve this, the first step involves collecting data on the material composition of vehicle components. This information is obtained from an internal SEAT IT system called the Material Information Sheet System (MISS), which is used across the Volkswagen Group and is comparable to similar systems employed by other automotive manufacturers. The material composition of the studied components was collected and analyzed by Iglesias-Émbil et al. (2020) [10]. However, it is important to note that the initial dataset in this study originates from the metallic composition of passenger vehicles, both ICEVs (Internal Combustion Engine Vehicles) and BEVs (Battery Electric Vehicles). Therefore, to estimate the quantity of each mineral in a truck whether diesel or electric a scaling factor must first be determined and applied, as shown in Eq. 1.

$$F_{scale} = \frac{C_j}{C_i} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Where F_{scale} represents the scaling factor between passenger vehicles and trucks. For BEVs, C_j and C_i refer to the battery capacity (kWh) of the truck and passenger vehicle, respectively. On the other hand, for ICEVs the scaling factor is calculated using the tank capacity in fuel liters. Once the total amount of metal per technology (combustion engine-fuel tank and electric motor-battery) has been calculated, the next step is to estimate the vehicle range in kilometres using Equation 2 (Eq. 2).

$$A_i = \frac{C_i}{EFC_i} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Where A_i represents the vehicle range in km, C_i is the capacity defined earlier, and EFC_i is the electric or diesel consumption per 100 km. The data regarding the technical characteristics of the vehicles, such as engine power (kW), battery capacity (kWh) or fuel tank capacity (L), electric or diesel consumption per 100 km, and truck payload capacity, have been obtained from digital technical datasheets as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of the vehicle type and data source. The first two are a passenger vehicle and a freight truck (ICEV), respectively, while the last two are a passenger vehicle and a freight truck (BEV) respectively.

Vehicle model	Power value (HP)
SEAT Leon 1.5 TSI (ICEV) [11]	150
Volvo FH16 (ICEV) [12]	780
CUPRA Born (NMC 811) (BEV) [13]	200
Tesla Semi (735.5 kW) (BEV) [14]	1000

Once the vehicle range in the study is known, the kilograms of material per kilometre travelled and per tonne of load transported can be calculated using Equation 3 (Eq. 3)

$$MCR_i = \frac{m_i}{A_i \cdot l_i} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

MCR is the metal consumption rate per technology, m_i is the mass of each metal component in the transportation means, A_i is the vehicle range calculated using Equation 2 (Eq. 2), and l_i is the transported load. It is worth noting that the range could be replaced by the total kilometres travelled over the entire service life of the vehicle. However, in the following section, 'Results and Discussion,' the range has been considered instead of the life-cycle distance, as the range directly reflects the vehicle's performance under specific operational conditions. This takes into account factors such as propulsion system efficiency, battery or fuel tank capacity, and the loads the vehicle is subjected to during use.

Finally, to obtain the exergy cost of the materials that make up the technologies under study, a physical parameter called *Thermodynamic Rarity* (TR), defined by Valero and his team [15], has been used. This parameter is a universal and stable unit of measurement, reflecting the physical criticality of mineral resources, which is based on the second law of thermodynamics, with a particular focus on the concept of exergy [16]. This concept aims to assess the mineral capital of the metals composing the study parts. This criterion has been proposed as an alternative to mass for the evaluation of materials because it assigns a higher value to those substances that are more valuable from a physical point of view [17]. The exergy cost, evaluating the manufacturing of the materials of the transport means, is calculated using Equation 4 (Eq. 4), where EC_i is the exergy cost for the analyzed system, m_i is the mass of each metal that constitutes the transport means, and TR_i (kJ/g) is the *Thermodynamic Rarity* obtained in previous studies [18] by summing the embodied exergy (kJ/g) and the exergy replacement cost (kJ/g).

$$EC_i = MCR_i \cdot TR \cdot m_i \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

4. Results and discussion

Using the information provided by the MISS Tables and the transport data from digital technical datasheets, the amount and percentage of the different elements contained in each of the analyzed components were determined: the engine and fuel tank of an ICEV freight transport and the motor and battery of a BEV freight transport. Figure 1 shows the exergy distribution, measured by *Thermodynamic Rarity*, of the elements composing the transport's parts.

Fig. 1. Exergy costs (MJ metal/km range · tonne of payload) calculated by *Thermodynamic Rarity* (MJ) of elements composing the freight transport studied parts (engine and fuel tank of a Volvo FH16 diesel truck (left figure) and the motor and battery of a Tesla Semi electric truck (right figure))

Fig. 1 shows the contribution of the exergy cost of the metals that make up the transportation systems analyzed. It can be observed that in heavy road ICEV transport (left figure), aluminum (Al) represents 77.63% of the total exergy cost. This is not due to the *Thermodynamic Rarity* of aluminum, but rather its significant mass presence within the system. Other metals with smaller contributions include Cu, Fe and Ni, although their exergy impact is significantly lower due to their smaller proportion in the vehicle composition in the case of Fe, and a lower *Thermodynamic Rarity* (*TR*) value in the case of Cu and Ni. On the other hand, in heavy BEV transport (right), the exergy impact of aluminum decreases to 31.23%, while other metals become more relevant. In particular, cobalt (Co), nickel (Ni), and copper (Cu) present contributions of 31.33%, 17.22%, and 9.97%, respectively. This change reflects the higher presence of these metals in batteries and electrical systems of the BEV, increasing their exergy impact compared to the ICEV. Moreover, in the BEV system, strategic elements such as palladium (Pd) and tantalum (Ta) acquire considerable relevance. This is due to their high *TR* values (2870013.09 kJ/g for Pd and 485911 kJ/g for Ta).

Fig. 2. Analysis of exergy (MJ metal/km range · tonne of payload) and material (kg metal/km range · tonne of payload) costs for heavy-duty road transport: ICEV vs. BEV

In Fig. 2, the total exergy and mass of all the metals composing the two studied technologies: the engine and fuel tank for the ICEV heavy-duty road transport (Volvo FH 16 D16B520), and the engine and battery for the BEV heavy-duty road transport (Tesla Semi 1000 HP) are shown. Additionally, it is observed that electric freight transport is significantly superior both in terms of exergy cost and material per kilometre and tonne transported. The material cost is higher for the electric truck due to its larger dimensions and higher power compared to the diesel truck (1000 HP versus 780 HP). However, the difference in exergy cost is due to the fact that the most valuable metals from a thermodynamic standpoint are found in the electrical and electronic vehicle devices, and since the electric truck has more such elements, its exergy cost is higher.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, the results reflect a shift in the material composition of heavy road transport systems: while the ICEV exhibits a higher exergy impact associated with aluminum due to its high mass presence, the BEV shows a greater reliance on strategic metals with higher *Thermodynamic Rarity*. This shift has significant implications for the availability and sustainability of mineral resources, particularly in the context of the electrification of the transport sector.

The increase in the exergy cost of the electric truck is primarily attributed to the presence of valuable metals, such as those used in the vehicle's electrical and electronic devices. This difference highlights the importance of optimization in design and material

selection to reduce the thermodynamic impact of electric technologies. Although the electric truck has higher material and exergy costs, advances in battery technology and the efficiency of electrical systems may lead to a reduction in these costs in the future. Furthermore, long-term sustainability and emission reduction could make the overall benefits of electric transport outweigh the current disadvantages. The difference in exergy cost underscores the importance of critical materials in the transition to electric transport. This emphasizes the need to develop innovative solutions that minimize the use of these materials or optimize their performance to improve the sustainability of heavy-duty electric transport.

6. Future Research Directions

Future research will focus on hydrogen fuel cell vehicles, which could not be addressed in this study due to the lack of available information regarding material composition in this technology. Additionally, the present study aims to be expanded to other modes of transportation, such as trains and ships, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the environmental and material impacts across various transportation sectors.

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